

Horizon 2020

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: As an input dataset, it will be summed up to get the total values for Vienna and afterwards computed the percentage of each age group, to be comparable to the data from Austria.

Dataset Population by age group: As an input dataset, it will be filtered for data about Austria and the age groups split up to be the same as for Vienna.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: It's the output of the project and used for a diagram.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: The data is distributed with some csv files. The collaboration, long-term preservation and re-use should be no problem since it's a simple text format and also standardised.

Dataset Population by age group: The file is provided as tsv file. Again the collaboration, long-term preservation and re-use should be no problem since it's a simple text format and also standardised.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: The output data are csv files and png pictures which also can be opened by nearly every software. Therefore again collaboration, long-term preservation and re-use should be no problem, because they are simple and widely used formats which are standardised.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Re-used

Dataset Population by age group: Re-used

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Created

What is the origin of the data?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Magistrate of Vienna

Dataset Population by age group: Eurostat

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Own Created Data

What is the expected size of the data?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: 1,5MB

Dataset Population by age group: 25KB

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: 86KB

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Everyone who is interested in the population of Vienna. People responsible for building places to live, people who want to buy flats, government etc. . There are many possible scenarios to reuse it, one of them is for further city planning.

Dataset Population by age group: Governments to compare the life quality in Europe or insurances and banks to calculate risks, news.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: People interested in the population. Specially, it can help to answer the question who is living in the city and who on the country. (If we might think that more families living on the countryside)

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: None

Dataset Population by age group: None

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Yes Handle / DOI

What naming conventions do you follow?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

- `data/raw` - Folder containing the external data
 - `data/processed` - Folder to store the results
 - `reports` - Folder to store the diagrams
- Additionally there exists an readme describing everything.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

- Austria
- Vienna
- Age distribution

Do you provide clear version numbers?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: According to the Metadata of this project there will be no version update

Dataset Population by age group: According to Eurostat there are yearly updated versions but Eurostat as publisher is responsible for versioning

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: There is mainly one version of the Data published, small fixes in git aren't directly connected with the output data

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline,

please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

Dataset Population by age group:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain data sets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: External Data.

Dataset Population by age group: External Data.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Yes, externally for everyone

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: The data will be shared on github (https://github.com/schmidii/data_experiment) and wit DOI's (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376).

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Normal text editor sufficient.

Dataset Population by age group: Normal text editor sufficient.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: In the end the data is saved as png and csv therefore nothing special is needed. (Texteditor, Image viewer)

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: No there is no documentation needed.

Dataset Population by age group: No there is no documentation needed.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: No there is no documentation needed.

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: The code for reproducing the experiment will be public for everyone to access.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?
Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: (not certified)

Dataset Population by age group: (not certified)

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: (not certified)

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: No because this is not needed because of the small amount of data.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Everyone they are published under cc-by-4.0

Dataset Population by age group: Everyone.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Everyone, I will also published under cc-by-4.0 license so it is also possible to access and use it.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: The data is open to everyone therefore there can't be an unauthorised access.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: python e.g.
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins

Dataset Population by age group:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: tsv
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: python e.g.
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: csv, png
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: python, image viewer
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

- Discipline-specific standards, classifications etc. are used: Dublin Core Metadata schema

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Attribution (BY)

Dataset Population by age group: Public domain (CC0)

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Attribution (BY)

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

The data will be available immediately after finishing the project, there is no reason why keeping them secret for any time.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: Everyone who is interested in the population of Vienna. People responsible for building places to live, people who want to buy flats, government etc. . There are many possible scenarios to reuse it, one of them is for further city planning.

Dataset Population by age group: Governments to compare the life quality in Europe or insurances and banks to calculate risks, news.

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: People interested in the population. Specially, it can help to answer the question who is living in the city and who on the country. (If we might think that more families living on the countryside)

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: Till the end of the summer term (1.7.2019).

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Personnel: Some time to publish the data and designing them in a way that they can be reused and interpreted.

Other: Free storage capacity of github for publishing the data.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The personal costs will be covered by the lecture data stewardship.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

I (David Schmidt, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3129-6719>), because I am the only person actively involved.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Preservation decisions

- David Schmidt

Costs

Personnel: The time needed to publish everything.

Other: Storage capacity (Free).

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

There are no special provisions for the data. From the lecture there is the additional provision that the data needs to get a DOI assigned as well as it has to be hosted on github. But the

data does not involve sensitive data therefore it can be stored online and transferred without any problem.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose: (not certified)

Dataset Population by age group: (not certified)

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna: (not certified)

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

Dataset Population by age group:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

There are no ethical concerns, the base data is already publicly shared, and my project is only abstracting the data and not adding some dangerous information. The data from Vienna is published under cc-by-4.0 and therefore it can be edited viewed etc. from everyone by only mention the origin. The other data set is published for reuse publicly.

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Dataset Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Population by age group:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Austria vs. Vienna:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

There are no other producers for data management directly involved. For the input data the according organizations are responsible for their data management, but for my newly produced data nobody else is involved.